

THE STAYER
Sociality and knowledge in disrupted worlds
Toward a sociology of collective boundary conditions

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Problem statement

Multiple and omnipresent crises, disruptions, uncertainty, instability, and risk have become a common place in diagnoses of modern times. According to theoretical traditions like *risk society and late modernity theories* (originating in Beck 1986; and Giddens 1990), *polycrisis* (Homer-Dixon et al. 2022; Tooze 2022), or *liquid modernity* (Bauman 1991; Bauman 2000), living in this world of global crises produces confusion, loss of agency, erosion of trust, crisis of meaning. People feel disorientated, alienated, and disconnected – a world of constant global Strangers.

My project challenges this vision, and its criticism targets the very core of such theories – the approach to the society as a whole, a single homogenous entity experiencing the single crisis. This approach blends disruptive technologies and artificial intelligence, climate change and pandemics, wars and economic volatility into all-embarrassing condition of polycrisis, risk, or uncertainty. Such *global crisis* is everywhere and nowhere simultaneously; it has no single face, no shared horizon, no common enemy or condition, and is experienced as diffuse, mediated, abstract.

Meanwhile, farmers suffering from draught in the African continent countries do not live through the same crisis as European students confused with deep fakes and echo chambers, Gaza citizens face different threat than Pacific islanders resisting the raising ocean. Pure mathematics does not work here: many smaller crises do not yet constitute one global crisis; they remain distinct and unique

Such *local, concrete cases* of middle-range, massive, and durable disruption, affecting multiple domains of collective life and experienced by communities staying in their homelands have one essential difference: they become shared tangible experience of concrete communities, where one

and the same disruption hits an entire community simultaneously and is experienced directly, synchronously, concretely. Awareness of the global climate change affects us differently than falling bombs we hide from together with our peers.

My pilot study of Russia's war against Ukraine (Yasna 2025) and, partly, existing literature from resilience studies and ethnographies of wars and terror (e.g. Lubkemann 2008; Solnit 2009; Gayer 2018) suggest that even intense crises lived through collectively do not simply produce mistrust, disorientation, or constant anxiety as polycrisis theorists claim. All these are present – especially at the initial stages of disruption; however, as the condition lasts and becomes a shared horizon of everyday life, communities develop new forms of orientation. Everyday life continues even amidst the most intense warfare, social order persists, morality does not dissolve, and social life does not turn into a war of all against all. Instead, communities mobilize, agency increases, collective action intensifies, people get situational clarity and know concretely what they are dealing with and become able to continue a fulfilling meaningful life amidst disruption.

Crucially, it is not only sociality that persists yet transforms; the very structure of everyday knowledge underlying it transforms with it: its pre-reflective background is disrupted and social reality must be continuously and explicitly reconstructed, epistemic practices accelerate and multiply, trust is reconfigured, moral knowledge becomes ambivalent – and inhabitants of this condition themselves change as epistemic subjects.

Hypothesis

May we then think of war and other societal catastrophes as a state that "suspends morality" (Levinas 2007, 21) and collapse social life into mere survival? Or should we rather assume that although being "the realm of uncertainty" (Fon Clausewitz 1976, 111), these are "socially transformative condition[s]," non-reducible to struggle and violence (Lubkemann 2008, 251)?

Or, probably, we should hypothesize that these two configurations of crises produce different epistemic and practical effects: while *abstract global risk* tends to generate confusion, informational overload, and weakened coordination, conditions of a *shared, concrete, and collectively experienced disruption*, when the entire social life is coordinated around the same problem, reorganizes the structure of sociality and knowledge itself. Initial breakdown and disorientation do occur, yet they progressively give way to practical clarity and congruence.

New forms of sociality and knowledge evolve. In terms of **sociality**: solidarity increases, collective agency and social integrity are restored, new forms of communal action arise, and new types of communality emerge. In terms of **knowledge**: epistemic practices accelerate and multiply, trust is reconfigured, moral orientation shifts, and inhabitants of this condition become new kinds of epistemic subjects.

This contrasts with how global crisis is theorized as: informational overload, anxiety, erosion of trust, and loss of agency.

	Distributed global crisis	Collective boundary condition
Structure	many different crises addressed as a global risk, uncertainty, or a polycrisis	one shared disruption
Experience	abstract, mediated	direct, embodied

	Distributed global crisis	Collective boundary condition
Knowledge	uncertainty, overload	situational clarity
Agency	paralysis, confusion (often theorized)	mobilization, coordination
Sociality	Fragmentation, detachment, alienation	intensified co-orientation and reconstruction of reality

This suggests that the *structure, or the mode of distribution* of crisis matters more than its *scale*: we can potentially imagine a single yet civilization-scale catastrophe like Covid-19 pandemic – and we may say, the world handled it in much more coordinated way than one might have expected.

Why it matters

Collective staying under massive disruption is not singular or exceptional. Prolonged collective staying under radical disruption and instability remains a widespread and increasingly characteristic condition of contemporary life – yet emerging not as a all-encompassing global condition of risk or polycrisis but as a growing multiplicity of locally shared boundary conditions, affecting hundreds of millions of people worldwide.

Additionally, this condition is not temporary state that will eventually resolve into normality – for millions of people, it is simply life itself, sustained across generations. It shapes how entire communities think, act, and constitute their collective identity. The question is not how communities *deal* with disruption and return to normal, but how they *live* within it – and what kind of social world they build and sustain while doing so.

Moreover, these communities are not isolated: they travel, write, and participate in global culture and discourse, bringing their experience and their ways of orienting in the world into the broader social fabric.

Understanding this condition is therefore not only a matter of understanding a specific population in a specific crisis – it is a matter of understanding something that increasingly permeates and shapes contemporary social life as a whole.

Existing research

If this suggestion is true, it reveals a major theoretical gap: we have multiple *macro-theories* of a global crisis society, while lacking adequate *middle-range* perspectives explaining how collective orientation, knowledge, and sociality are maintained in the patchy society of numerous local crises. The subject matter looks similar, yet the emphasis is opposite.

There are several bodies of literature that may be partly applicable here, yet these existing works just highlight the theoretical gap.

Mobility bias

First, the kind of crisis described above – shared, locally experienced, and structuring everyday life as a durable condition – can only be observed from within communities that remain in place, since only under such conditions can disruption become a common and sustained horizon of collective life.

Meanwhile, a large part of crises- and disruption-related scholarship is shaped by a strong “mobility bias” (e.g. criticism by Schewel 2020), focusing predominantly on displacement, migration, or veterans returning home, while paying comparatively little attention to those who “simply” remain in place. And still, even under intense disruption, most people remain in place, and communities continue to inhabit their shattered worlds.

For example, even Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine -- one of the most durable and intense contemporary armed conflicts -- displaced over 15 million, yet 5.5 million have since returned, and over 30 million never left. This means 75 per cent staying¹ while their world crashed across multiple dimensions: material, infrastructural, political, social, moral.

Reduction of the stayers' experience

When those who stay are addressed, it is mostly in three ways.

The first spotlight is on **population-level dynamics**, the demographical consequences of disruption, and the policy responses to them (e.g. criticism by Brighton 2011).

On the other hand, there is rich body of phenomenological and experience-oriented studies, which provide detailed descriptions of **individual lived experience** under extreme conditions (e.g. Konecki 2024; Leociak 2025; Bataeva 2026), but do not address the collective organization of social life under disruption.

And finally, the experience of staying is predominantly approached in the **reduced terms** of trauma or coping. Those who stay are being depicted as frightened, suffering, anxious; their life is supposed to be reduced to bare survival and basic needs, while everything beyond is suspended. Wars and disasters are approached as mere *breakdowns* of the social communities have to survive, endure, or get through - not as meaningful social *conditions* with their own internal logic.

Outside view

Even resilience approaches – probably the closest to the subject matter proposed – focus on the factors and capacities enabling communities to survive and recover from disruption, rather than a condition of collective staying as a distinct social phenomenon with its own structure, the specific forms of sociality and collective identity it produces, and what it does to shared knowledge and collective orientation.

Research questions

In sum, no sociological theory exists for this condition.

This gap pushes us toward essential theoretical questions that remain almost untouched both in classical and modern sociological thought.

- How do communities *sustain* shared meanings, social order, collective knowledge, and everyday orientation when instability and disruption become not an episode but a durable condition of everyday life?
- Through what social and epistemic *practices* do communities staying amidst disruption transform initial disorientation into workable forms of orientation, making this condition livable and to not descend into a state of pure survival, savagery, and chaos?

¹ Based on UNHCR data, <https://www.unhcr.org/where-we-work/countries/ukraine>

- And ultimately, what *social type* and forms of collective identity does this condition produce?

Without such understanding, we cannot adequately grasp conditions that are no longer exceptional but increasingly widespread.

Theoretical foundations

To theorize this condition, the project introduces the concept of **collective boundary condition** – a massive, multi-dimensional, and collectively shared disruption that becomes a durable horizon of everyday life for an entire community. To analyze what this condition produces and how communities live through it, the project makes **two theoretical inversions** – deliberate reversals of foundational assumptions within two established traditions.

First, it constructs a genealogy of sociological *boundary figures* – a constellation of conceptual figures rarely placed under the same roof: from the classical Stranger (Simmel 1908; Schutz 1944)([Simmel 1908](#); [Schutz 1944](#)) and the Homecomer (Schutz 1945)([Schutz 1945](#)), to figures of marginality (Du Bois 2007 [1903]; Stonequist 1937; Park 1928), voluntary or forced mobility (Park 2024 [1925]; Bauman 2011), outsiders and exclusion (Wood 1934; Waśkiewicz 2008), or belonging to several social worlds simultaneously (like Kruszewski's Borderlander (Halicka 2019)). Continuing this genealogy, the project introduces a new boundary figure – *the Stayer*, which *inverts* the classical configuration and invites us to reconsider the concept of boundaries in sociology. It is not an individual detached from a stable community and social world, but an entire community remaining in place and continuing everyday life while their shared world becomes unstable and is continuously shattered and destabilized across multiple dimensions.

Second, to analyze what this condition does to shared knowledge and collective orientation, the project draws on *phenomenological sociology* and *phenomenologically grounded sociology of knowledge* – and this requires a *second inversion* that would enable it to address this new figure. [A rich tradition stretching from the classical figures to recent works](#) (e.g. Tuomela 2007; Costello 2014; Zahavi 2025) [has developed detailed accounts of sociality, collective orientation, and shared knowledge – yet consistently within what they variously call “natural and normal human world-life”](#) (e.g. Husserl 1970 [1936], 16, 119, 149), [normal everyday state](#) (Schutz et al. 1983, 146), [or “normal state of affairs”](#) (Berger et al. 1966, 93).

The project readjusts phenomenological perspective toward conditions of radical instability, where no such normality can be presupposed. By doing this, it invites us to challenge a widespread claim that extreme experiences – war included – appear as limit problems hardly accessible for the phenomenological method (Steinbock 1998; Depraz 2003; Wehrle 2018; e.g. contemplations by Geniusas 2022) and reconsider the very limits of applicability of social phenomenology.

Together, these two inversions place both source perspectives – a genealogy of boundary figures and phenomenological sociology, including sociology of knowledge – into a context of collectively experienced radical disruption under conditions where it becomes a shared and collectively experienced horizon of social life, for which neither was originally intended.

Operationalization

The project develops an approach to analyzing the condition of staying articulated within the theoretical framework.

- First, it **operationalizes** the Stayer as a social configuration along two analytical axes: a *macro-level* specification of the contexts of massive and durable disruption that enable the Stayer condition to emerge, and a *micro-level* specification of who counts as a Stayer within them. These axes provide criteria for empirical case selection across different historical and social settings.
- Second, it offers a set of **sensitizing concepts** (Blumer 1992 [1969]) derived from the theoretical framework and adjusted through the pilot empirical study. [Second, it offers a set of sensitizing concepts \(ibid.\) derived from the theoretical framework and adjusted through the pilot empirical study.](#)

Together, these two contributions make the theoretical framework empirically tractable – providing criteria for case selection and analytical tools for empirical inquiry.

Theoretical model

The project elaborates on the interpretive sociological theory with middle-range scope (in Merton's (1949) sense). It defines a specific type of social condition which produces a specific social figure; both can be empirically identified through a set of operational criteria and investigated through a set of sensitizing concepts.

Key concepts. The theoretical core of the project stands on the conceptual pair:

- **Collective boundary condition** is a type of socio-historical condition of (i) massive multi-dimensional disruption of normal social order that (ii) persists beyond initial shock and becomes a durable horizon of everyday life, and (iii) is experienced collectively by local communities to nations and, hypothetically, humanity as a whole and (iv) constitutes a common existential horizon rather than an aggregate of parallel individual crises or differentially distributed risks, as theorized in risk society or polycrisis perspectives. It designates a context that constitutes the condition of possibility for the emergence of *the Stayer*.
- **The Stayer** is a collective sociological boundary figure; a social form, designating communities that (i) physically stay in place, (ii) remain embedded in their affected social world, and (iii) are engaged in everyday life and continue ordinary everyday practices under *collective boundary condition*.

Scope and empirical referents. This theory encompasses conditions of middle-range, massive, and durable disruption, affecting multiple domains of collective life and experienced by communities staying in their homelands – such as wars, occupations, violent political regimes, staying in climate-threatened regions, depopulating rural areas, or destroying city districts. Applies to mid-term and long-term cases where disruption becomes a persistent horizon of everyday life, not an episodic event.

Core problem. The theory addresses the persistence and transformation of social order, sociality, and shared knowledge under such conditions – specifically, how communities maintain collective orientation and social integrity, sustain shared meaning and everyday practices, and reorganize themselves as epistemic and social actors when the taken-for-granted background of everyday life is durably destabilized.

Key proposition / argument. Unlike global crises, risks, and general uncertainty, under conditions local middle-range crises and disruptions, communal life is not suspended or reduced

to chaos or bare survival; social order persists, “normal” everyday life continues, and collective agency often increases.

Mechanism. The condition of collective staying under massive disruption does not produce a single, uniform effect, but unfolds through two stages:

- **Stage 1. Initial breakdown.** When massive disruption first strikes, people can no longer rely on habitual routines and implicit knowledge to navigate their world. This stage is marked by:
 - *disorientation and defamiliarization* – familiar reality no longer "works" as before
 - *forced époque* – the collectively experienced, situationally imposed suspension of the taken-for-granted, where what was previously automatic and unquestioned suddenly demands conscious attention

This stage is real and should not be minimized, yet under conditions of collectively shared, boundary situation, it tends to be brief. This is precisely where the Stayer condition diverges from what global risk theories describe: abstract, distributed crisis tends to sustain this stage indefinitely, producing permanent confusion and loss of agency. Collectively shared, concrete disruption does not.

- **Stage 2. Reorientation and reconstruction.** As the condition persists and becomes a durable horizon of everyday life, communities develop new forms of orientation through a set of interconnected processes:
 - *Ambivalence* – the stable coexistence of two seemingly incompatible states or realities, "normal" and disrupted, which does not dissolve into a new natural attitude but becomes a stable, livable feature of everyday life.
 - *Ongoing renegotiation of normality* – repeatedly redefining what counts as "normal," "safe," or "livable" under changing circumstances.
 - *Ongoing social reconstruction of reality* – restoring shared orientation and social intelligibility, collective meaning, repairing social coordination, and sustaining everyday life under altered conditions; this includes the transformation of epistemic practices, trust, and moral orientation through which communities reorganize themselves as epistemic subjects.

Outcome: Social order and knowledge do not collapse but persist in a transformed form. Everyday life continues under altered conditions. *Collective agency* often increases rather than diminishes. New forms of *collective identity* emerge from the shared work of sustaining a livable world. New *epistemic subjects* emerge – communities whose knowledge, trust, and moral orientation have been permanently reshaped by the condition they have lived through. This outcome – oriented, agentic, socially coherent communities living through massive disruption – is what the Stayer framework is designed to explain.

Empirical cases and research design

War case. The present doctoral study develops the first empirical instantiation of this agenda based on the case of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine. It introduces the concept of *narrative reconstruction of reality* (rephrasing Bruner 1991) – one of the forms of the reconstruction of reality intrinsic to the Stayer condition – and explores it through a theory-driven qualitative analysis of civilian wartime diaries (2022-2026).

The dissertation develops a *corpus approach* to this type of data. Unlike most diary-based research, which draws on several sources read in depth, this study constructs a systematic corpus of publicly shared civilian wartime diaries, treating them not as individual testimonies but as a collective source. This makes visible the collective narrative work of a community under disruption, which no single testimony can provide.

Occupation case. Alongside the dissertation, my parallel study applies the same framework to the situation of staying under occupation of Ukrainian territories through in-depth interviews, which extends the agenda to a different context and data type, and demonstrates the framework's transferability beyond the doctoral study.

Interdisciplinarity and transferability

The Stayer framework is **interdisciplinary** by constitution. *Theoretically*, it draws on classical and contemporary sociology, social phenomenology, and sociology of knowledge. The *empirical* design engages with literary and diary studies, narrative theory, and corpus methodology. And *practically*, the project extends into digital humanities and living archives scholarship.

Although this doctoral study addresses a concrete *case* (civilian staying in during full-scale Russia's war against Ukraine) and utilizes a concrete *methodological approach* (phenomenologically oriented qualitative analysis of the corpus of public wartime diaries), the framework remains **theoretically and methodologically open**. It can be applied across different *contexts* of disruption, from war and occupation to environmental crises and infrastructural decline. It is also compatible with a wide range *data types* and *analytical strategies* – from narrative and discourse analysis to oral histories, interviews, mixed-method approaches, and even surveys.

The project, thus, underlies a **broader research agenda**, which I plan to advance during the postdoc stage.

International collaboration

Since its first introduction at the VII Conference of the International Alfred Schutz Circle in April 2025, the Stayer framework has been presented at 4 invited talks and 9 international conferences across Poland, Austria, Germany, Ireland, Denmark, and Spain.

The project evolves in ongoing dialogue with colleagues at institutions including:

- Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Polish Academy of Sciences (Department of Theoretical Sociology)
- International Alfred Schutz Circle
- University of Vienna (Department of Sociology)
- University of Warsaw (Department of History of Social Thought)
- Institute for Human Sciences, Vienna (IWM)
- The Center for Subjectivity Research, University of Copenhagen
- The Centre for Interdisciplinary Ukrainian Studies “Denkraum Ukraine,” University of Regensburg
- Documenting Russia's War Against Ukraine (LivArch), Herder Institute for research on East Central Europe

- Institute of Philosophy, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

The project has received competitive **funding and fellowships** from NAWA, IWM, Denkraum Ukraine, LivArch, Center for Subjectivity Research, and German Society for Phenomenological Research.

Resources

- The versioned record of this research description: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036611>

- Project website: <https://thestayer.org>

- Project repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/thestayer>

- Author's ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2023-9732>

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